

Annamalai Series

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Annamalai Series

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{x-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} V_i^r x^i (x^{n-i} - 1).$$

Proof. The Annamalai series is derived from the following combinatorial geometric series [1-36].

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} V_i^{r+1} x^i = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} V_i^r x^i + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} V_{i-1}^r x^i + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} V_{i-2}^r x^i + \dots + \sum_{i=n-2}^{n-1} V_{i-(n-2)}^r x^i + \sum_{i=n-1}^{n-1} V_{i-(n-1)}^r x^i.$$

The expansion of combinatorial geometric series on the right-hand side is further expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} V_i^r x^i + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} V_{i-1}^r x^i + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} V_{i-2}^r x^i + \dots + \sum_{i=n-1}^{n-1} V_{i-(n-1)}^r x^i \\ &= (V_0^r x^0 + V_0^r x^1 + V_0^r x^2 + \dots + V_0^r x^{n-1}) + (V_1^r x^1 + V_1^r x^2 + V_1^r x^3 + \dots + V_1^r x^{n-1}) \\ &+ (V_2^r x^2 + V_2^r x^3 + V_2^r x^4 + \dots + V_2^r x^{n-1}) + \dots + V_{n-1}^r x^{n-1}. \\ & \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} V_i^{r+1} x^i = V_0^r \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^i + V_1^r \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} x^i + V_2^r \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} x^i + V_3^r \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} x^i + \dots + V_{n-2}^r \sum_{i=n-2}^{n-1} x^i + V_{n-1}^r \sum_{i=n-1}^{n-1} x^i. \end{aligned}$$

Now, it is concluded that

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} V_i^{r+1} x^i = \frac{1}{x-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} V_i^r x^i (x^{n-i} - 1).$$

Therefore, the Annamalai series is:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{x-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} V_i^r x^i (x^{n-i} - 1).$$

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